

GUIDE v.43.1 piecewise simple linear logistic regression tree (constant fitted to incomplete cases in terminal nodes) for predicting `is_fraud`. Largest pruned tree has no more than 3 terminal nodes. At each split, an observation goes to the left branch if and only if the condition is satisfied. $S_1 = \{\text{Drug_Stores_and_Pharmacies, Money_Transfer, Other, Wholesale_Clubs}\}$. Sample size (in *italics*), proportion of 1s in `is_fraud`, and name of regressor (with sign of slope) printed below nodes. Terminal nodes with proportions of 1s above and below value of 0.05 at root node are painted yellow and vermillion respectively. Second best split variable at root node is `merchant_state`.